

IR-spectrophotometric identification and quantification of nitrofurazone

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Abstract

Nitrofurazone is a synthetic semicarbazone from the nitrofuran class and exhibits activity against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. The aim of the current study includes the development and validation of a highly sensitive, fast, easy-to-perform, and non-destructive IR spectrophotometric method for the identification and quantification of nitrofurazone with respect to the analytical parameters of specificity, linearity, detection limit, quantitation limit, accuracy, and precision. Results show that at 1580 cm⁻¹ and at 1707 cm⁻¹, a linear relationship between absorbance and concentration was proven in the concentration ranges: 160 mg/1 g ÷ 240 mg/1 g, with correlation coefficients close to 1. The accuracy is better at 1580 cm⁻¹ (RSD < 0.9%) than at 1707 cm⁻¹ (RSD < 2.34%). Higher repeatability was obtained at 1580 cm⁻¹ (RSD < 2.75%) than at 1707 cm⁻¹ (RSD < 3.85%). At 1580 cm⁻¹ LOD = 12.32 mg/1 g; LOQ = 41.07 mg/1 g; at 1707 cm⁻¹: LOD = 14.79 mg/1 g; LOQ = 49.31 mg/1 g.

Keywords

accuracy, IR-spectrophotometry, nitrofurazone, precision, validation

Introduction

Pharmacological activity and application of nitrofurazone

Nitrofurazone (Nitrofurazone, Furacilin, 2-[(5-nitrofurazan-2-yl)methylene]diazanecarboxamide) (Fig. 1) is a semicarbazone of the type R-CH=NNH-CO-NH₂ (Nitrofurazone 2010).

Figure 1. Chemical structure of nitrofurazone (Nitrofurazone 2010).

The compound is a type of Schiff base and contains an azomethine group (>C=N-) in its chemical structure. Schiff bases were first studied by Hugo Schiff in 1864 (Fabrizzi 2020). The drug is obtained from the chemical reaction of 5-nitrofurazone with semicarbazide (Houshdar et al. 2003).

Nitrofurazone is a nitrofurazone derivative and possesses effective potential against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria such as staphylococci, streptococci, and dysentery bacillus. The biological activity of the drug is associated with the presence of the active pharmacophore (-CO-NHN=C-) in its chemical structure. The mechanism of action of nitrofurazone is based on its ability to suppress DNA synthesis and disrupt the metabolism of microorganisms (Grayson et al. 2012).

Nitrofurazone, as an antibacterial agent, is mainly used as an antiseptic for the local treatment of skin and mucous membrane infections:

- 1) Superficial skin infections and wound healing (Karapolat et al. 2020);
- 2) External ear infections: the compound is used in the form of drops or ointment for the treatment of otitis externa, especially when it is caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, or mixed bacterial flora (Douglass 1970).

The drug is also applied as a bladder irrigant. Urinary catheters coated with a matrix containing nitrofurazone have been used in an attempt to prevent catheter-associated urinary tract infections (Johnson et al. 1999). The activity of the compound against *Leishmania donovani*, *Leishmania major*, and *Leishmania enrietti* (Neal and Van Bueren 1988) has been investigated.

Recently, interest in topical therapy with nitrofurazone has been revived, as its application leads to the healing of resistant ulcers without observed adverse reactions. A poly-(vinyl alcohol) hydrogel, cross-linked with glutaraldehyde and impregnated with 0.2% nitrofurazone for topical use, has been developed (Vila et al. 2014).

Although the topical use of nitrofurazone-containing preparations has been found to be highly effective in the treatment of various bacterial skin infections, its use is associated with an excessive frequency of hypersensitivity reactions. Possible adverse reactions with topical application include local allergic reactions, such as contact dermatitis (Sanz-Cabanillas et al. 2024), including foot contact dermatitis, redness, rash, swelling, or inflammation (Ozkaya and Ekinci 2016). This necessitates the development of reliable methods for controlling the amount of the compound in these products in order to ensure quality.

The drug is listed in the California Act, shows clear evidence of mutagenicity and carcinogenicity in animal studies (Hiraku et al. 2004), and is withdrawn from human use and restricted for application in aquatic products (NTP 1988).

The main metabolite of nitrofurazone is semicarbazide, which is formed in aquatic products by endogenous mechanisms, especially in aquatic crustaceans, and can enter the body with them. Semicarbazide has been found in various types of food (animal and non-animal sources) and in the environment, which raises concerns about food safety. Although, due to proven carcinogenic and teratogenic harmful effects on humans, the drug is prohibited in veterinary medicine, nitrofurazone and its carcinogenic metabolite, semicarbazide, have been found in honey, meat, and seafood. This can be a health risk for people consuming these foods who are known to have hypersensitivity to nitrofurans (Sanni et al. 2024). In connection with the increased illegal use of nitrofurazone in foods of animal origin, it is important to increase the control of the content of the compound in order to ensure the safety of consumers' health when using animal foods.

Methods for analysis of nitrofurazone

The following methods for analysis of nitrofurazone have been reported:

- 1) Spectrophotometry (Sastry et al. 1992);
- 2) Fluorometry (Taniguchi et al. 1974): nitrofurazone dissolved in dimethylformamide is determined at $\lambda_{\text{excitation}} = 245 \text{ nm}$ and $\lambda_{\text{emission}} = 445 \text{ nm}$;
- 3) Gas chromatography (Ryan et al. 1975);
- 4) High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with UV detection (Tubino M et al. 2009);
- 5) HPLC method with photodiode detection (HPLC-DAD) (Shaalán and Belal 2010; Ibrahim et al. 2023);
- 6) HPLC with post-column chemiluminescent detection (Satieperakul et al. 2017).

Spectrophotometric methods for analysis of nitrofurazone

For the analysis of nitrofurazone, spectrophotometric methods based on the formation of colored products include (Sastry et al. 1992):

- 1) Determination of the product formed by the reduction of nitrofurazone with 3-methylbenzothiazolin-2-one hydrazone in the presence of iron (III) chloride at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 600 \text{ nm}$;
- 2) Reaction of the hydrolysis product of nitrofurazone with thiobarbituric acid at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 520 \text{ nm}$;
- 3) Reaction of the hydrolysis product of nitrofurazone with barbituric acid at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 440 \text{ nm}$;
- 4) Oxidation of nitrofurazone with excess N-bromosuccinimide and determination of the consumed N-bromosuccinimide using methyl-isonicotinic acid hydrazide at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 620 \text{ nm}$.

Chromatographic methods for analysis of nitrofurazone in pharmaceutical products

The recommended method for the determination of nitrofurazone in topical pharmaceutical preparations, such as ointments, is a high-performance liquid chromatographic method. The drug in topical ointments has been analyzed by HPLC under chromatographic conditions: octadecylsilane column with a particle diameter of $10 \mu\text{m}$, mobile phase: distilled water : acetonitrile : triethylamine buffer = 790 : 200 : 10 v/v/v, flow rate: 2 mL/min, injection volume 20 μL , UV detection at wavelength $\lambda = 365 \text{ nm}$, elution time: 8 min (Tubino M et al. 2009).

For the simultaneous determination of nitrofurazone and lidocaine hydrochloride, an HPLC method has been used on a Zorbax Eclipse XBD C18 column ($4.6 \text{ mm} \times 150 \text{ mm} \times 5 \mu\text{m}$), mobile phase: 0.025 M disodium hydrogen phosphate : methanol : triethylamine = 70 : 30 : 0.1 v/v/v (pH = 4.0), flow rate: 1 mL/min, and UV detection at wavelength $\lambda = 374 \text{ nm}$ for nitrofurazone and $\lambda = 322 \text{ nm}$ for lidocaine hydrochloride (Shaalán and Belal 2010).

HPLC is often applied for the analysis of other nitrofurans. For the quantitative determination of nitrofurantoin and phenazopyridine in human urine samples, a HPLC method has been reported with a reversed-phase C18 column (150 mm × 4.6 mm × 5 μm), a gradient eluting mobile phase consisting of 5 mmol/L sodium dihydrogen phosphate and acetonitrile at a flow rate of 1 mL/min, and UV detection at a wavelength $\lambda = 370$ nm (Ibrahim et al. 2023).

Chromatographic methods provide high selectivity, accuracy, and precision but have disadvantages, such as specific equipment, analysis duration, and high cost. The development of methods that are highly sensitive, rapid, easy to perform, and non-destructive with respect to the components tested is important because this would contribute to the improvement of the quality of nitrofurazone powdered products for topical use and to increasing the effectiveness of market control in the case of illegal use of nitrofurazone in powdered foods of animal origin. The method that is characterized by these advantages is infrared spectrophotometry.

Infrared spectrophotometry

Infrared spectrophotometry is a physical instrumental method for qualitative and quantitative analysis and for testing impurities in drugs. The method is based on the interaction of infrared (IR) radiation with matter. The infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum covers the wave numbers from 12800 cm⁻¹ to 10 cm⁻¹ and is divided into near, mid, and far regions. The mid-infrared region extends from 4000 cm⁻¹ to 200 cm⁻¹. The group frequency region covers a region from 3600 cm⁻¹ to 1200 cm⁻¹, where identical functional groups absorb in a certain range of wavenumbers. Another range is the fingerprint region from 1200 cm⁻¹ to 700 cm⁻¹, and it reflects the absorptions from the skeletal structure of the molecule. Overtones and component frequencies are also observed. For the infrared region, the spectrum is presented as a dependence of the percentage of transmission [T (%)] on the wavenumber (cm⁻¹). The advantages of IR are the non-destructive nature of the drug under study, rapid analysis, accuracy, and precision. In recent years, the advantages of IR over other analytical techniques have increased its application in various fields of analytical science (Stephanos and Addison 2017).

The European Medicines Agency recommends a guideline for the use of infrared spectroscopy by the pharmaceutical industry (European Medicines Agency Guideline 2014).

The most common application of IR in the pharmaceutical industry is for quality control of pharmaceutical products (Boiret and Chauchard 2017) by identification and quantification (Meza et al. 2006) of active drug compounds in tablets (Igne et al. 2015).

Infrared spectroscopy is used for quality control of:

- 1) Substances: amoxicillin (Fanelli et al. 2018) and cefepime dihydrochloride (Bugay et al. 1996);
- 2) Tablets: caffeine (Laasonen et al. 2003), diclofenac (Scheiwe et al. 1999), nimesulide (Rocha et al. 2010);
- 3) Capsules: cefadroxil (de Marco and Salgado 2016).

The application of infrared spectroscopy in pharmaceutical technology (Jamrogiewicz 2012) is for monitoring the following pharmaceutical manufacturing processes (De Beer et al. 2011):

- 1) Determination of powder density (Román-Ospino et al. 2016);
- 2) Quantification of tablet content uniformity (Blanco et al. 2006);
- 3) Determination of narcotic substances, such as cocaine and heroin (Ravbery 1987).

The validation and application of accurate analytical methods for quantification of nitrofurazone content in various powdered products would contribute to strengthening quality control and ensuring the safety of consumption by manufacturers. The reliability of the methods must be confirmed by validating them with respect to analytical parameters in order to ensure acceptable linearity, accuracy, and precision in quality control when applied.

The aims of the current study include the development and validation of a highly sensitive, fast, easy-to-perform, and non-destructive IR spectrophotometric method for the identification and quantification of nitrofurazone with respect to the analytical parameters specificity, linearity, detection limit, quantitation limit, accuracy, and precision; application of the IR method for determination of nitrofurazone in model mixtures by the calibration curve method.

Materials for the determination of nitrofurazone by the IR spectrophotometric method

Tested compounds:

- 1) Nitrofurazone reference substance: Sigma Aldrich, N: 1878Va;
- 2) Nitrofurazone test substance: Alfa Alcer N: 13104830;
- 3) Potassium bromide (KBr) substance. Specac, N: 250-011, P/N 3610.

Before analysis, the substances nitrofurazone and potassium bromide were dried at 120 °C to constant weight.

Methods – IR spectrophotometric method for determination of nitrofurazone

Apparatus

IR spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher).

Preparation of model mixtures with nitrofurazone for study of analytical parameter linearity

Accurately measured amounts of 140 mg, 160 mg, 170 mg, 180 mg, 200 mg, 220 mg, and 240 mg of nitrofurazone substance were mixed separately with potassium bromide

substance up to 1.0 g to obtain model mixtures with increasing nitrofurazone content in the range: 140 mg/1 g ÷ 240 mg/1 g.

Preparation of model mixtures with nitrofurazone for study of analytical parameter accuracy (precision)

Three samples of three model mixtures with different nitrofurazone concentrations (80%–120%) from the range of specifications of the most common concentration of nitrofurazone in products (0.2%) were prepared.

Accurately measured amounts, respectively: 160 mg/1 g (80%) (N160), 200 mg/1 g (100%) (N200), and 240 mg/1 g (120%) (N240) of nitrofurazone substance were mixed separately with potassium bromide substance up to 1.0 g to obtain model mixtures with nitrofurazone content in the interval: 160 mg/1 g ÷ 240 mg/1 g.

Preparation of model mixtures with nitrofurazone for the study of analytical parameter internal precision (repeatability)

Precisely measured amounts, respectively: 160 mg/g (80%) (N_{160}), 200 mg/g (100%) (N_{200}), and 240 mg/g (120%) (N_{240}) of nitrofurazone substance were mixed separately with potassium bromide substance up to 1.0 g to obtain model mixtures with a nitrofurazone content in the range: 160 mg/1 g ÷ 240 mg/1 g.

Statistical method of the root mean square error

To determine the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ), the data for the measured absorbance, obtained for model mixtures with increasing concentrations of nitrofurazone, were subjected to linear regression analysis, and the regression equation $y = a \cdot x + b$ was obtained, from which the concentration of nitrofurazone was calculated for each studied model mixture.

Results and discussion

Identification of nitrofurazone

The identity was confirmed by the fact that in the spectrum of nitrofurazone in the model mixtures, similar characteristic frequencies were observed as in the spectrum of the nitrofurazone reference substance (Fig. 2).

From the IR spectrum of nitrofurazone are visible very weak bands for the C–H stretching vibrations at 3310 cm^{-1} , and 3260 cm^{-1} (Wang 1968); weak asymmetric stretching (ν as N–H = 3520 cm^{-1}), weak symmetric stretching (ν s N–H = 3480 cm^{-1}) (Hemalatha 2011); and strong stretching vibrations ν C=N at 1580 cm^{-1} (Suydam 1963).

Figure 2. Spectrum of nitrofurazone reference substance.

The stretching vibration of the C=O group is one of the most intense. Its frequency is about 1707 cm^{-1} . For nitrofurazone, C=O group vibrations are observed at 1708 cm^{-1} and 1718 cm^{-1} for the spectrum in *nujol* and at 1717 cm^{-1} for the spectrum in a potassium bromide tablet (Wang 1968). Due to the strongest stretching vibrations being ν C=N at 1580 cm^{-1} (Suydam 1963) and ν C=O at 1710 cm^{-1} , these characteristic frequencies were used for validation of analytical parameters (Wang 1968).

The validation of the IR spectrophotometric method for the determination of nitrofurazone was performed in accordance with the guidelines of the ICH Q8 (R2) (International Conference on Harmonisation 2009) to demonstrate the suitability of the method for its intended purpose. The following validation parameters were investigated: specificity, linearity, range, accuracy, precision (repeatability), limit of detection, and limit of quantitation (Mark et al. 2002).

Validation of analytical parameter specificity

A placebo sample containing only potassium bromide without nitrofurazone was analyzed by the IR spectrophotometric method. The spectrum of potassium bromide is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Spectrum of potassium bromide.

The specificity of the method is confirmed by the lack of measurable absorbance of the placebo sample with potassium bromide at the characteristic frequencies for nitrofurazone.

Validation of analytical parameters' linearity, detection limit, and quantitation limit

The analytical parameter linearity was studied by measuring the absorbance of model mixtures with nitrofurazone at the most characteristic frequencies: 1580 cm^{-1} (ν C=N) and 1707 cm^{-1} (ν C=O). Samples with increasing concentrations of nitrofurazone were analyzed: 140 mg, 160 mg, 170 mg, 180 mg, 200 mg, 220 mg, and 240 mg in the range: 140 mg/1 g \div 240 mg/1 g. Table 1 shows data for: C [mg/1 g] – nitrofurazone content in model mixtures; CKBr [mg/1 g] – potassium bromide content in model mixtures; A – measured absorbance.

Table 1. Absorbances of model mixtures of nitrofurazone at 1580 cm^{-1} and 1707 cm^{-1} .

C [mg/1 g]	C _{KBr} [mg/1 g]	A 1580 cm^{-1}	A 1707 cm^{-1}
140	860	0.169	0.204
160	840	0.207	0.249
170	830	0.220	0.259
180	830	0.235	0.267
200	800	0.281	0.312
220	780	0.318	0.344
240	760	0.334	0.360

The results of the obtained absorbances for model mixtures with increasing concentration of nitrofurazone were subjected to linear regression analysis for the study of the analytical parameter linearity. The regression equations were obtained: $y = a \cdot x + b$; y – absorbance, x – concentration [mg/g], a – slope, b – intercept.

The linearity calibration curves for the model mixtures with nitrofurazone at 1580 cm^{-1} and at 1707 cm^{-1} are presented in Fig. 4.

The calculated correlation coefficients (R^2) are close to 1. The obtained regression equations at 1580 cm^{-1} and 1707 cm^{-1} prove the linear relationship between the absorbance (A) and the concentration C [mg/1 g] in the corresponding concentration intervals: 160 mg/1 g \div 240 mg/1 g (Fig. 4).

Parameters of regression equations for nitrofurazone at 1580 cm^{-1} and at 1707 cm^{-1} are described in Table 2.

Table 2. Parameters of the regression equations for nitrofurazone at 1580 cm^{-1} and at 1707 cm^{-1} .

N:	Parameter	1580 cm^{-1}	1707 cm^{-1}
1.	Linear interval	140 mg/1 g \div 240 mg/1 g	
2.	Regression equation	$y = 0.001727 \cdot x - 0.07117$	$y = 0.001582 \cdot x - 0.01115$
3.	Slope (a)	0.001727	0.00158
4.	Standard error of the slope	$8.28 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$9.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$
5.	Intercept (b)	0.007117	0.01115
6.	Standard error of the intercept	0.01572	0.01727
7.	Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.9886	0.9838
8.	Standard deviation	SD = 0.007093	SD = 0.007791
9.	Limit of detection	LOD = 12.32 mg/1 g	LOD = 14.79 mg/1 g
10.	Limit of quantitation	LOQ = 41.07 mg/1 g	LOQ = 49.31 mg/1 g

Similar data were obtained for the limit of detection and limit of quantitation (Table 2): at 1580 cm^{-1} : LOD = 12.32 mg/1 g; LOQ = 41.07 mg/1 g; at 1710 cm^{-1} : LOD = 14.79 mg/1 g; LOQ = 49.31 mg/1 g. The LOD and LOQ data are lower than 160 mg/1 g and indicate that nitrofurazone can be identified and determined in the range: 160 mg/1 g \div 240 mg/1 g.

Validation of analytical parameters' accuracy and internal precision (repeatability)

In Table 3, for model mixtures, data are summarized for: 1) measured amount of nitrofurazone: 160 mg/1 g (80%) (N_{160}), 200 mg/1 g (100%) (N_{200}), 240 mg/1 g (120%) (N_{240}); absorbances of nitrofurazone for the study of analytical parameters' accuracy and internal precision (repeatability): $A_{N_{160}}$, $A_{N_{200}}$, $A_{N_{240}}$.

Spectra of nitrofurazone in model mixtures are illustrated in Fig. 5 (80%), Fig. 6 (100%), and Fig. 7 (120%). The experimental results for the absorbances of nitrofurazone at specific frequencies are presented in Table 4 (80%), Table 5 (100%), and Table 6 (120%).

Figure 4. Linearity for nitrofurazone at 1580 cm^{-1} and at 1707 cm^{-1} .

Table 3. Absorbances of model mixtures of nitrofurazone for the study of analytical parameters' accuracy and internal precision.

N:	N_{160}	N_{200}	N_{240}	N_{160}	N_{200}	N_{240}
	[mg/1 g]	[mg/1 g]	[mg/1 g]	[mg/1 g]	[mg/1 g]	[mg/1 g]
	1580 cm^{-1}			1707 cm^{-1}		
1.	158	195	235	158	195	235
2.	160	200	238	160	200	238
3.	162	205	240	162	205	240
N:	$A N_{160}$	$A N_{200}$	$A N_{240}$	$A N_{160}$	$A N_{200}$	$A N_{240}$
1.	0.206	0.272	0.329	0.246	0.308	0.353
2.	0.207	0.280	0.334	0.245	0.308	0.353
3.	0.208	0.291	0.340	0.254	0.319	0.373
X	0.207	0.281	0.334	0.248	0.312	0.360
SD	0.001	0.01	0.006	0.005	0.006	0.01
RSD [%]	0.48	3.56	1.80	2.02	1.92	2.78
SX	0.0006	0.006	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.006
t.SX	0.002	0.02	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.015
$\bar{X} - t.SX$	0.205,	0.261,	0.326,	0.240,	0.304,	0.345,
$\bar{X} + t.SX$	0.209	0.301	0.342	0.256	0.320	0.375

Figure 6. Spectrum of a model mixture with 200 mg/1 g (100%) nitrofurazone.

The content of nitrofurazone was obtained by the method of calibration curve. In Table 7 (1580 cm^{-1}) and Table 8 (1707 cm^{-1}) data for: N – number of measurements; $[N_{160}]$, $[N_{200}]$, $[N_{240}]$ – obtained amount of nitrofurazone in the model mixtures; $R[N_{160}]$, $R[N_{200}]$, $R[N_{240}]$ – analytical yield (degree of recovery) (%); \bar{X} : arithmetic mean value; SD: standard deviation; RSD (%): relative standard deviation; S: root mean square error; P: confidence probability (%); t: Student's coefficient; $\bar{X} - t.SX$, $\bar{X} + t.SX$ – confidence interval, are presented.

Figure 7. Spectrum of a model mixture with 240 mg/1 g (120%) nitrofurazone.**Table 4.** Frequencies and absorbance of a model mixture with 160 mg/1 g (80%) nitrofurazone.

Frequencies [cm^{-1}]	Absorbance A	Frequencies [cm^{-1}]	Absorbance A	Frequencies [cm^{-1}]	Absorbance A
3456.9477	0.1160	1455.5185	0.3042	903.0380	0.2591
3153.0552	0.0981	1389.4170	0.2055	819.7842	0.2743
3134.8704	0.1080	1346.9110	0.3474	806.9174	0.2218
3122.3640	0.1049	1324.5525	0.3890	785.0313	0.2194
2900.2547	0.1065	1312.8936	0.3785	759.7264	0.2181
2883.7354	0.1073	1250.0307	0.3503	736.2478	0.2959
1707.1941	0.2544	1196.6303	0.3884	665.9142	0.1006
1580.9326	0.2082	1147.1553	0.2300	653.6173	0.1102
1537.0387	0.0994	1019.6276	0.2901	593.5937	0.1675
1501.2728	0.2381	968.2434	0.2736	581.6279	0.0997
				547.8491	0.1119

Table 5. Frequencies and absorbance of a model mixture with 200 mg/1 g (100%) nitrofurazone.

Frequencies [cm^{-1}]	Absorbance A	Frequencies [cm^{-1}]	Absorbance A	Frequencies [cm^{-1}]	Absorbance A
3457.3617	0.1625	1455.3919	0.3960	911.2636	0.1763
3152.6413	0.1420	1389.3391	0.2880	902.5559	0.3682
3134.6658	0.1583	1346.9987	0.4870	819.5309	0.3810
3121.9598	0.1538	1324.4064	0.5130	806.6788	0.3190
2900.9170	0.1561	1312.3043	0.5136	784.9047	0.3188
2884.7094	0.1572	1249.7823	0.4638	759.4001	0.3147
1706.9068	0.3186	1196.0118	0.5196	735.9118	0.4080
1682.7610	0.1950	1146.9800	0.3288	665.7779	0.1559
1580.9326	0.2910	1019.5399	0.4131	651.3430	0.1723
1500.5910	0.3162	967.8100	0.3762	593.3891	0.2439
				549.5049	0.1937

The analytical parameter accuracy (precision) reflects the degree of correspondence between the average result obtained from repeated analyses and the accepted true value (International Conference on Harmonisation 2009).

Three samples of three model mixtures with different concentrations were analyzed separately by the IR spectrophotometric method. The absorbances, amounts of nitrofurazone, SD, and RSD were determined. The accuracy is represented by the degree of recovery: \bar{R} [%] \pm RSD [%].

The results show that with a confidence probability of P = 95% ($t = 2.57$), all experimental data for \bar{R} [%] \pm RSD [%] are included in the corresponding interval: 1580 cm^{-1} (Table 7): 100.68% \pm 0.89% (160 mg/1 g, 80%); 101.96% \pm 0.31%

Table 6. Frequencies and absorbance of a model mixture with 240 mg/1 g (120%) nitrofurazone.

Frequencies [cm ⁻¹]	Absorbance A	Frequencies [cm ⁻¹]	Absorbance A	Frequencies [cm ⁻¹]	Absorbance A
3456.9770	0.1876	1346.6334	0.5599	902.5462	0.4356
3134.8022	0.1817	1323.9438	0.6208	819.4822	0.4463
2899.9235	0.1797	1312.3140	0.6252	806.6301	0.3763
2883.8328	0.1816	1249.6167	0.5623	784.8560	0.3725
1706.2104	0.3729	1195.5394	0.6244	759.3514	0.3681
1683.0580	0.2272	1146.4296	0.3989	735.7949	0.4836
1580.8937	0.3405	1019.2818	0.4864	665.8558	0.1886
1500.0602	0.3693	967.7905	0.4560	651.0069	0.2035
1455.0266	0.4764	911.7165	0.2123	593.0044	0.2673
1389.2271	0.3432			549.2468	0.2236

Table 7. Investigation of analytical parameters accuracy and internal precision for nitrofurazone at 1580 cm⁻¹.

N:	[N ₁₆₀] [mg/1 g]	R[N ₁₆₀] [%]	[N ₂₀₀] [mg/1 g]	R[N ₂₀₀] [%]	[N ₂₄₀] [mg/1 g]	R[N ₂₄₀] [%]
1.	160.49	101.58	198.71	101.90	231.71	98.60
2.	161.07	100.67	203.34	101.67	234.61	98.58
3.	161.65	99.78	209.71	102.30	238.08	99.20
X ± SD	161.07 ± 0.58		203.92 ± 5.52		234.8 ± 3.19	
\bar{R} [%] ± RSD [%]		100.68 ± 0.89		101.96 ± 0.31		98.79 ± 0.35
SD	0.58	0.90	5.52	0.32	3.19	0.35
RSD [%]	0.36	0.89	2.71	0.31	1.36	0.35
SX	0.34	0.52	3.19	0.18	1.84	0.20
P [%]	95.0	95.0	95.0	95.0	95.0	95.0
t	2.57	2.57	2.57	2.57	2.57	2.57
t.SX	0.87	1.34	8.2	0.46	3.6	0.51
X- t.SX, X+ t.SX	160.20, 161.94	99.34, 102.02	195.72, 212.12	101.5, 102.42	231.2, 238.4	98.28, 99.30

Table 8. Investigation of analytical parameters' accuracy and internal precision for nitrofurazone at 1707 cm⁻¹.

N:	[N ₁₆₀] [mg/1 g]	R[N ₁₆₀] [%]	[N ₂₀₀] [mg/1 g]	R[N ₂₀₀] [%]	[N ₂₄₀] [mg/1 g]	R[N ₂₄₀] [%]
1.	162.55	102.88	195.40	100.21	230.18	97.95
2.	161.92	101.20	195.40	97.70	230.18	96.71
3.	167.60	103.46	208.69	101.80	242.83	101.18
X ± SD	164.02 ± 3.11		199.83 ± 7.67		234.4 ± 7.30	
\bar{R} [%] ± RSD [%]		102.51 ± 1.14		99.90 ± 2.07		98.61 ± 2.34
SD	3.11	1.17	7.67	2.07	7.30	2.31
RSD [%]	1.90	1.14	3.84	2.07	3.11	2.34
SX	1.80	0.68	4.43	1.20	4.22	1.34
P [%]	95.0	95.0	95.0	95.0	95.0	95.0
t	2.57	2.57	2.57	2.57	2.57	2.57
t.SX	4.63	1.75	11.39	3.08	10.85	3.44
X- t.SX, X+ t.SX	159.39, 168.65	102.76, 104.26	188.44, 211.22	96.82, 102.98	223.55, 245.25	95.17, 102.05

(200 mg/1 g, 100%); 98.79% ± 0.35% (240 mg/1 g, 120%) at RSD < 0.9%, which proves that there are no sharply different results; 1707 cm⁻¹ (Table 8): 102.51% ± 1.14% (160 mg/1 g, 80%); 99.90% ± 2.07% (200 mg/1 g, 100%); 98.61% ± 2.34% (240 mg/1 g, 120%); at RSD < 2.34%, which proves that better accuracy is obtained at 1580 cm⁻¹: RSD < 0.9% (Table 7).

The analytical parameter internal precision (repeatability) reflects the degree of coincidence or closeness of correspondence of the results of successive measurements of the same quantity in the analysis of samples taken from one homogeneous sample when applying the same methodology under repeated conditions in a short time. Repeatability is characterized by the uncertainty of the result (uncertainty of result), which includes SD, RSD, and confidence interval ($\bar{X} \pm t.S\bar{X}$) (International Conference on Harmonisation 2009).

Experimental results show that at a confidence probability P = 95% (t = 2.57), all data for the quantities obtained correspond to the respective confidence interval: 1580 cm⁻¹: RSD [%]: 0.36% (160 mg); 2.71% (200 mg); 1.36% (240 mg) (Table 4); 1707 cm⁻¹: RSD [%]: 1.90% (160 mg); 3.84% (200 mg); 3.11% (240 mg) (Table 8).

From the results, it is obvious that better repeatability is obtained at 1580 cm⁻¹: RSD < 2.75% (Table 7) than at 1707 cm⁻¹: RSD < 3.85% (Table 8).

Conclusion

For improvement of the quality of nitrofurazone powdered products for topical use and to increase the effectiveness of market control in the case of illegal use of nitrofurazone in foods of animal origin, the development of non-destructive methods with high sensitivity would be of scientific and applied importance. The IR spectrophotometric method for the determination of nitrofurazone has been validated in terms of the analytical parameters: specificity, linearity, LOD, LOQ, accuracy, and internal precision. The linear relationship between absorbance and concentration was proven in the concentration ranges: 160 mg/1 g ÷ 240 mg/1 g at 1580 cm⁻¹ and 1707 cm⁻¹, with correlation coefficients close to 1. The accuracy is greater at 1580 cm⁻¹ (RSD < 0.9%) than at 1707 cm⁻¹ (RSD < 2.34%). The experimental results for analytical parameter repeatability are obtained at 1580 cm⁻¹ (RSD < 2.75%) than at 1707 cm⁻¹ (RSD < 3.85%). At 1580 cm⁻¹ LOD = 12.32 mg/1 g; LOQ = 41.07 mg/1 g; at 1707 cm⁻¹ LOD = 14.79 mg/1 g; LOQ = 49.31 mg/1 g. The validated IR spectrophotometric method is non-destructive with respect to the tested component, fast and easy to perform, with acceptable accuracy and repeatability, and is suitable for the identification and quantification of nitrofurazone in order to strengthen quality control in powdered products for topical use and in powdered food products of animal origin.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declare that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declare that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declare that no informed consent was obtained from humans, donors, or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declare that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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